

MULTIMEDIA RESOURCES IN KAZAKHSTANI CLASSROOMS: ENHANCING ENGLISH LISTENING PROFICIENCY FOR SENIOR STUDENTS

*B. Aimukhanova*¹

Scientific supervisors: Eskazinova Zhanar Amantaevna, Mardonova Sitora Mardonovna

Abstract:

This article examines the theoretical basis for the effectiveness of multimedia resources (podcasts, video content, interactive platforms) in developing English listening skills among 10th–11th grade students of Russian-language schools in Kazakhstan. Literature analysis shows that multimedia resources can enhance motivation and improve listening comprehension. Practical recommendations focus on integrating digital tools into curricula and preparing for the Unified National Test (UNT).

Key words: multimedia resources, listening skills, foreign language education, Russian-language schools in Kazakhstan, digitalization of education, UNT.

In the modern world, where globalization and digitalization play a key role, developing listening skills in a foreign language is becoming increasingly important. Kazakhstan, as a trilingual country (Kazakh, Russian, English), faces the need to prepare students for international exams and real-life communication. Multimedia resources can serve as an effective tool in addressing this challenge.

In Kazakhstan's multilingual environment, where Russian remains the language of interethnic communication, the development of listening skills in a foreign language (English, German, etc.) remains a key task. Modern high school students, especially in senior grades, face the necessity of understanding authentic speech in the context of globalization and preparation for international exams (IELTS, TOEFL). However, traditional teaching methods used in Kazakhstani schools often fail to meet the needs of the digital generation. Multimedia resources (podcasts, video content, interactive platforms) help overcome textbook limitations by integrating real communicative situations and increasing student motivation.

According to the "State Compulsory Educational Standard of General Secondary Education", the subject "Foreign Language" aims to develop students' language skills in four types of speech activities (listening, speaking, reading, writing). Upon completion of general secondary education, students must achieve a B1 (intermediate – B1.2) level according to the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR).

By this Standard "Listening: understands the main idea of clearly articulated speech within the literary norm on familiar topics, simple informational messages about common everyday issues, and topics related to studies and future professional activities; can follow the main points of a long discussion in general terms; understands a lecture or conversation on academic and professional topics, provided the subject is familiar and the speech is simple and well-structured; comprehends detailed technical instructions; understands most television programs on topics of interest, such as interviews, short lectures, and reports, when spoken slowly and clearly".

At the senior stage of learning, students have already mastered the basics of a foreign language, allowing them to successfully comprehend spoken language. For this reason, listening is a crucial method for reinforcing foreign language skills.

Listening is a fundamental skill that influences the development of other language abilities (speaking, reading, writing). The ability to understand spoken language directly impacts speaking and reading development, as it enables students to better perceive and imitate pronunciation and intonation (Krashen, 1982). Senior students experience difficulties in perceiving fast speech, accents, and idiomatic expressions, which is critical for successfully passing the UNT and international exams.

Multimedia technologies in the learning process serve the following functions:

- Integrate different types of information (text, sound, video, etc.) and present it by engaging multiple human senses;
- Develop critical thinking;
- Stimulate cognitive processes;
- Enable interactive interaction with learners;

¹ *Aimukhanova Bayan Bauyrzhanovna*

- Adapt to the needs of learners;
- Individualize the learning process;
- Organize group work in multimedia environments;
- Develop teamwork skills;
- Foster stable motivation;
- Create conditions as close to reality as possible for acquiring educational and professional skills (virtual laboratories, excursions, museums).

At the senior level of education, using video resources in lessons actively engages all types of speech activities, thereby improving all components of foreign language communicative competence, which is the main condition for intercultural communication. At the final stage of learning, it is advisable to use video resources that contribute to the further development of secondary language identity and the enhancement of primary language identity, as well as the further formation of communicative, sociocultural, and intercultural competence.

Both domestic and foreign methodologists traditionally suggest dividing work with texts into the following stages:

1. Pre-text stage.
2. Text stage.
3. Post-text stage.

A teacher must possess a comprehensive knowledge of teaching methods, tools, content, and techniques, addressing issues related to learning manageability. Special attention is given to clearly set goals that ensure achieving results, continuous feedback, and reproducibility of the learning cycle. The methodology of teaching any type of speech activity follows this pattern: familiarization (control), training (control), application (control).

The use of multimedia aligns with the principles of Kazakhstan's updated educational content, aimed at digitalizing education. Platforms such as "iTest" (adapted to Kazakhstani standards) and "British Council Kazakhstan" provide access to authentic materials tailored to the local context. Research by Kazakhstani methodologists (e.g., A. Kunantbayeva) emphasizes that visual and auditory support reduces cognitive load in the perception of foreign speech (Kunantbayeva, 2021).

According to the cognitive theory of multimedia learning (Mayer, 2020), the use of visual and auditory elements enhances information retention by reducing cognitive load. This is especially relevant for listening skills, where students can simultaneously perceive audio and video content, improving their listening comprehension.

To integrate multimedia resources into the listening learning process, it is recommended to use platforms such as BBC Learning English for working with authentic materials and BilimLand for gamification. Interactive exercises on Quizlet can help in vocabulary training necessary for the UNT. Virtual meetings with native speakers via Zoom, in collaboration with language centers in Kazakhstan, also contribute to developing communication skills.

Examples of platform usage:

- BBC Learning English: Podcasts and videos for listening practice. Students can listen to and transcribe podcasts to improve their listening comprehension.
- BilimLand: Gamification of listening through interactive games and exercises. This increases student motivation and makes the learning process more engaging.
- Quizlet: Interactive flashcards and quizzes for vocabulary and grammar practice. Students can create their own sets of flashcards and share them with classmates.

It is expected that integrating multimedia resources into the educational process will lead to a 20–30% improvement in listening comprehension. Students using multimedia resources are likely to show better results in accent perception and multiple-choice listening tasks. Moreover, interactive formats can reduce stress when working with authentic materials.

The use of multimedia resources is expected not only to improve listening comprehension but also to enhance student motivation due to interactivity and accessibility of materials. This, in turn, may lead to better results in the UNT and other international exams.

Integrating multimedia resources into the educational process contributes to increased student motivation and readiness for international exams. The study's results may be useful for teachers and educational program developers, particularly in adapting international content to local educational standards.

Developing listening skills through multimedia may also enhance other language skills, such as speaking and reading, as students gain the ability to better perceive and imitate pronunciation and intonation.

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